

Agro2Circular

D7.14 – Financing Recommendations (Draft)

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1. List of Abbreviations

AVALAM	Unión de empresarios Murcianos SGR
BBI JU	Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking
BGK	Bank Gospodarstwa Krajowego
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CARM	Comunidad Autónoma Región de Murcia
CDC	Caisse des Dépôts Groupe
CDP	Cassa Depositi e Prestiti
CE	Circular Economy
CERSA	Compañía Española de Reafianzamiento
CF	Cohesion Fund
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EC	European Commission
ECBF	European Circular Bioeconomy Fund
EFSI	European Fund for Strategic Investments
EGFF	European Growth Finance Facility
EIAH	European Investment Advisory Hub
EIB	European Investment Bank
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ETC	European Territorial Cooperation
EU	European Union
GEF	Global Environment Facility
GNI	Gross National Income
GPP	Green Public Procurement
IBRD	International Bank for Reconstruction and Development
ICO	Instituto de Crédito Oficial
ICREF	Instituto de Crédito y Finanzas de la Región de Murcia
ICSID	International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes
IDA	International Development Association
IFC	International Finance Corporation
INFO	Instituto de Fomento de la Región de Murcia
JICE	Joint Initiative on the Circular Economy
JTF	Just Transition Fund
KfW	Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
MIGA	Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
MSWM	Municipal Solid Waste Management
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPV	Net Present Value
R&D	Research and Development
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SMP	Single Market Programme
SRSP	Structural Reform Support Programme

UN United Nations
WBG World Bank Group

2. Executive Summary

This document constitutes deliverable 7.14 *Financing Recommendations (Draft)* of the Agro2Circular project, undertaken within task 7.5 *Multidimensional model for adoption, replicability and scalability of A2C systemic solution at regional and EU level*, and represents the main outcome of sub-task 7.5.3 *Financing schemes linked to the business models generated*. This is a first draft version of the financing recommendations developed during the project that was submitted halfway through the project duration, in month 18.

As such, this document focusses in its analysis and recommendations primarily on international and regional financial frameworks that enable the circular economy. Deliverable 7.15 *Financing Recommendations* (due date M35) will then more closely align the analysis and recommendations with the concrete outcomes and results of the project. Nevertheless, dedicated sections present both public and private financing schemes in the region of Murcia, which marks the territorial centre of the Agro2Circular project. Agro2Circular is an EU (H2020) funded project that will implement a territorial, scalable, systemic and digitally powered solution for the upcycling of fruits and vegetables residues and non-renewable, multilayer plastic into high added value products.

This deliverable is a synthesis report summarising the main conclusions regarding financing schemes and recommendations for their improvement. The aim of the report is to provide an overview of the driving forces that can be used to partially or fully finance eligible businesses or projects in the circular economy. It analyses different types of financing schemes and best practices, exploring the financing ecosystem that enables the implementation of territorial circular solutions at European and regional level to ensure the territorial implementation of the project's systemic solutions. Recommendations are furthermore provided to improve the financing schemes analysed, including recommendations to promote public procurement in Agro2Circular related areas.

Chapter four explores international financing schemes for the circular economy, with a particular focus on the various funding programmes provided by the European Union. Other points of interest are international financial institutions and other for-profit initiatives, asset management firms and crowdfunding opportunities. Chapter five then focuses on green public procurement as key mechanism in enabling the transition towards the circular economy. Chapters six and seven present the above-mentioned public and private financing schemes in the Spanish region of Murcia. Chapter 9 is a selection of good financing practices, while, lastly, chapter 10 provides the name-giving financing recommendations.

3. Introduction

The world has reached a tipping point where it can no longer cope with the numerous human-made environmental pressures. According to Earth Overshoot Day data¹, the last time the world was able to sustain itself was in December 1971, while today all renewable resources are exhausted by 28 July. The famous 1972 Club of Rome report gave the issue a succinct and pragmatic slogan: The Limits to Growth².

It is no longer an option, the world must become more sustainable. One of the proposed models that enable the shift to a more sustainable future is the circular economy, as the necessary changes to resource exhaustion are not achievable within today's linear economic approach. While our current economic model is based on the linear function of extraction - production - usage - disposal, the circular economy aims to repair, reuse, and recycle today's valuable, but scarce, materials and resources. A fact that is also increasingly acknowledged by policy makers around the world. In Europe, the European Union announced its first Action Plan for the Circular Economy in 2015, and has since launched a new Action Plan consisting of 35 actions in 2020³ that emphasises above all that the economy is able to grow independently/decoupled from resource consumption.

Another global event that revealed the urgent need to more sustainable patterns of production and consumption was the Covid-19 pandemic. Disrupted supply chains highlighted the manyfold issues connected to the transport of materials over long distances. Reassessing and refocussing on internal resources also enables nations and regions to contribute to a more efficient use of resources and the reduction of transport-related emissions.

Although the transition to a circular economy is urgently needed, there are still many barriers. One of these is access to finance for circular economy models, not least due to the perception and assessment of risks, even though there is currently a growing financial interest in investing in circular economy business opportunities.⁴ Circular economy business models often require higher investment costs because they need to build up an infrastructure. Especially SMEs are confronted with this problem. They cannot make large investments themselves, and banks are often reluctant to finance circular economy initiatives with a long payback period. The lower return compared to linear business models is largely due to unpriced positive and negative externalities. The negative effects of linear products are often not priced in.⁵ Another related issue is the lack of data to base financing decisions on as reporting standards for circular solutions that show their benefits are still in their infancies.

¹ <https://www.overshootday.org/>

² Donella H. Meadows, Dennis L. Meadows, Jørgen Randers & William W., III, Behrens. 1972. *The Limits to Growth. A Report for the Club of Rome's Project on the Predicament of Mankind.*
https://collections.dartmouth.edu/teitexts/meadows/diplomatic/meadows_ltg-diplomatic.html

³ COM(2020) 98 final. 2020. *A new Circular Economy Action Plan. For a cleaner and more competitive Europe.* European Commission.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>

⁴ <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/financing-circular-economy>

⁵ <https://neosfer.de/en/financing-circular-economy/>

However, the circular economy offers investment opportunities not only because it is a proven policy response to pressing environmental and social challenges, but also for investment reasons. A study by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation concluded that in addition to increasing the resilience of supply chains, the circular economy offers significant growth opportunities. Adopting circular economy principles in Europe in the mobility, built environment and food sectors alone could generate annual benefits of €1.8 trillion by 2030.⁶ The circular economy furthermore promises a competitive advantage to manufacturing firms by reducing their reliance on materials and components.

The mechanisms for meeting the finance needs of the circular economy and to reorient capital from linear to circular solutions are becoming more diverse by the day. European Union funds, other global grants, beneficial instruments created by financial institutions with sustainable approaches, asset management funds, and the benefits of scaling up green public procurement practices are the main drivers for accelerating the transition to a circular economy. Other financial products and services to name are public equity funds, bonds, private market funds, banking, and crowdfunding.⁷

⁶ Ellen MacArthur Foundation. 2020. *Financing the Circular Economy. Capturing the Opportunity*. <https://emf.thirdlight.com/file/24/Om5sTEKOn0YUK.Om7xpOm-gdwc/Financing%20the%20circular%20economy%20-%20Capturing%20the%20opportunity.pdf>

⁷ <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/finance/overview>

4. International Financing Schemes for the Circular Economy

4.1 European Union Funds

The European Union had long been considered a pioneer in environmental protection when the von der Leyen Commission announced the European Green Deal in 2019. The declared goal of the Green Deal is to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. An ambitious goal for which the European Commission has identified the circular economy as a key to success – a term that first appeared in the late 1980s and was used by David Pearce and Kerry Turner in 1990 to describe an economic system around the valorisation of waste.⁸ Notwithstanding the fact that there is no finite definition of the circular economy, the concept is nowadays being taken up by policy makers around the world, and particularly in Europe, to respond to the unprecedented environmental challenges of the 21st century. The main framework for the circular economy in Europe today are the Circular Economy Action Plans (adopted in 2015 and 2019 respectively). 30% of the EU's €1,074.3 billion Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for the period 2021-2027 is to be spent on climate change. The same applies to the €750 billion of the EU's Next Generation Recovery Plan.⁹ It follows that there is currently a lot of EU funding supporting the transition to the circular economy.

The Union supports actors who want to research or invest in this field through various funding programmes such as the Horizon Europe programme, regional policy support, the LIFE programme, and the Single Market programme.

4.1.1 Horizon Europe

The main source of funding for research and innovation projects in Europe is Horizon Europe, the successor programme to Horizon 2020 in the MFF 2021-2027 and the largest European R&I funding programme to date with a budget of €95.5 billion. In line with the overarching policy strategy of the double transition, Horizon Europe's stated objectives are to “tackle climate change, help to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boost the EU's competitiveness and growth.”¹⁰ Participation is open to legal entities from the EU and associated countries.

Horizon Europe offers extensive and diverse funding opportunities. Its civilian part (as opposed to the European Defence Fund and EURATOM) is divided into three pillars, which in turn are subdivided into different funding areas and/or managing authorities. The three pillars are linked by the programme part “*Widening participation and strengthening the*

⁸ David W. Pearce & R. Kerry Turner. 1990. *Economics of Natural Resources and the Environment*.

⁹ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/the-eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget-2021-2027/>

¹⁰ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

European Research Area".¹¹ While Pillar I "*Excellent Science*" supports research and Pillar III "*Innovative Europe*" supports innovation, Pillar II "*Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness*" is about supporting the development of technologies subject to six clusters. In the context of this report, which was written as part of a project on the development of circular systemic solutions, the latter pillar is therefore particularly worth highlighting. However, in terms of corporate technology adoption, it should be noted that 70% of the Horizon Europe budget for SMEs is allocated to the European Innovation Council, a 'one-stop shop' whose aim is to lend "support to innovations with breakthrough and disruptive nature and scale up potential that are too risky for private investors"¹².

Another new element of Horizon Europe compared to Horizon 2020, alongside the European Innovation Council, are the EU Missions, which are cross-disciplinary "portfolios of actions" designed to support the EU's strategic priorities, such as the European Green Deal.¹³ In addition to funding programmes, an action portfolio can also include, for example, policies and regulations.

The five main mission areas are:

1. **Adaptation to climate change, including societal transformation** – Targets by 2030: prepare Europe to deal with climate disruptions, accelerate the transition to a healthy and prosperous future within safe planetary boundaries and scale up solutions for resilience that will trigger transformations in society.
2. **Cancer** – Targets by 2030: more than 3 million more lives saved, living longer and better, achieve a thorough understanding of cancer, prevent what is preventable, optimise diagnosis and treatment, support the quality of life of all people exposed to cancer, and ensure equitable access to the above across Europe.
3. **Healthy oceans, seas, coastal & inland waters** – Targets by 2030: cleaning marine and fresh waters, restoring degraded ecosystems and habitats, decarbonising the blue economy in order to sustainably harness the essential goods and services they provide.
4. **Climate-neutral & smart cities** – Targets by 2030: support, promote and showcase 100 European cities in their systemic transformation towards climate neutrality by 2030 and turn these cities into innovation hubs for all cities, benefiting quality of life and sustainability in Europe.
5. **Soil health & food** – Targets by 2030: at least 75% of all soils in the EU are healthy for food, people, nature and climate. The proposed mission combines research and innovation, education and training, investments and the demonstration of good practices using "Living labs" (experiments and innovation in a laboratory on the ground) and "Lighthouses" (places to showcase good practices).¹⁴

¹¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/ec_rtd_he-investing-to-shape-our-future_0.pdf

¹² Ibid.

¹³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe_en

¹⁴ European Commission. 2021. *Horizon Europe - Investing to shape our future* [Fact sheet]. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/ec_rtd_he-investing-to-shape-our-future_0.pdf

Although all these issues are related in some way to the circular economy approach, there are concrete opportunities for action in the area of circular economy, particularly under Missions 1, 4 and 5.

4.1.2 Regional Policy Support

Next to Horizon Europe, regional policy support is another major instrument for financing the circular economy in the EU as it can contribute to “increased recycling, improved waste management, resource and energy efficiency, strengthening the bioeconomy, novel product design solutions, new business models and green job creation”¹⁵.

These policy supports were commonly known as European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) in the previous programming period. Between 2021-2027, efforts have been made to simplify and yet expand these funds. The main funds to be mentioned for the purposes of this report are the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund (CF), as well as REACT-EU and the Just Transition Fund (JTF).

For the period 2021-2027, the EU regional or cohesion policy identified 5 priorities with a total allocated budget of €392 billion (as opposed to the 11 thematic objectives of the previous funding period):

1. a more competitive and smarter Europe,
2. a greener, low carbon transitioning towards a net zero carbon economy,
3. a more connected Europe by enhancing mobility,
4. a more social and inclusive Europe,
5. a Europe closer to citizens by fostering the sustainable and integrated development of all types of territories.¹⁶

The list of bodies and organisations that can benefit from regional funding includes public bodies, certain private sector organisations (especially small businesses), universities, associations, NGOs and voluntary organisations. Foreign companies located in the region of the respective operational programme can also apply, provided they comply with European public procurement rules.

Funding via the European Regional Development Fund is subject to a shared responsibility between the European Commission and the Member States authorities (national and regional). “Based on their prosperity, all regions and Member States will concentrate the support on a more competitive and smarter Europe, as well as greener, low-carbon transitioning towards a net zero carbon economy and resilient Europe, through the mechanism known as 'thematic concentration'.” No less than 30% of all ERDF operations are expected to contribute to climate objectives.¹⁷

In contrast, the Cohesion Fund specifically targets the less developed Member States, a categorisation that is measured as a Gross National Income (GNI) per capita of less than 90% of the EU-27 average. Currently, the Cohesion Fund covers Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Poland,

¹⁵ <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/financing-circular-economy>

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/2021-2027_en

¹⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en

Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia. It is expected that 37% of the total Cohesion Fund allocation will contribute to climate objectives.¹⁸

The Just Transition Fund is a new instrument of Cohesion Policy 2021-2027 and supports the territories most affected by the transition to climate neutrality.¹⁹ REACT-EU (Recovery Assistance for Cohesion and the Territories of Europe) is one of the largest programmes under the new NextGeneration EU instrument, with a budget of €50.6 billion. “It continues and extends the crisis response and crisis repair measures delivered through the Coronavirus Response Investment Initiative and the Coronavirus Response Investment Initiative Plus and constitutes a bridge to the long-term recovery plan.” To create the right conditions for recovery, it should also be possible to support investments that contribute to the transition to a digital and green economy as well as infrastructure.²⁰

4.1.2.1 *Interreg Europe*

Another instrument that supports European regional policy is Interreg Europe. It is the Union’s instrument to support cooperation between regions and countries (European Territorial Cooperation) and is part of the C-part of the ETC, which aims to enhance the effectiveness of Cohesion Policy.

Interreg Europe is an interregional cooperation programme co-financed by the European Union that aims to reduce disparities in development, growth, and quality of life within and between European regions in the 27 EU Member States, plus Norway and Switzerland. With a budget of €379 million, it supports local, regional and national governments across Europe to develop and implement better policies across 2021-2027. One of the main themes of this programme is ‘Greener Europe’, with a special focus on the circular economy. It contributes to all EU priorities and aims to improve regional governance through capacity building.

Public bodies such as national, regional and local authorities as well as organisations relevant to regional development policy such as regional development agencies, innovation agencies, chambers of commerce, environmental agencies, energy agencies, NGOs, universities and/or research centres can benefit from this programme.²¹

4.1.3 LIFE

In 1992, the European Union created a dedicated financial instrument to fund environmental and climate action – the LIFE programme. In the current funding period, it has been allocated a budget of €5.4 billion and consists of four sub-programmes:

1. Nature and Biodiversity
2. Circular Economy and Quality of Life
3. Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation
4. Clean Energy Transition²²

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/cohesion-fund_en

¹⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/just-transition-fund_en

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/react-eu_en

²¹ <https://www.interregeurope.eu/what-is-interreg-europe>

²² https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life_en

“The Circular economy and quality of life sub-programme aims at facilitating the transition toward a sustainable, circular, toxic-free, energy-efficient and climate-resilient economy and at protecting, restoring and improving the quality of the environment, either through direct interventions or by supporting the integration of those objectives in other policies.”²³

The mechanisms of funding are the Standard Action Projects (SAPs) and Strategic Integrated Projects (SIPs). The former targets projects implementing innovation or best practices solutions, while the latter targets policy and legislation actions.

4.1.4 Single Market Programme (SMP)

The Single Market is one of the central pillars of the European Union and the largest market in the world that enables people, goods, services and money to move freely between countries. For 2021-2027, the Commission has proposed “a dedicated €4.2 billion programme to empower and protect consumers and enable Europe’s many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to thrive”.²⁴

The objectives of the SMP are to:

1. Maintain a high level of food safety;
2. Give even higher protection to consumers;
3. Boost the competitiveness of businesses, in particular SMEs;
4. Improve the governance of the Single Market and compliance with rules;
5. Produce and disseminate high-quality statistics;
6. Develop effective European standards.²⁵

Of particular relevance for this report is the food safety focus area of the Single Market Programme, which represents 41% of the programme’s budget. Its expected impacts are to:

1. Prevent, control and eradicate animal diseases and plant pests;
2. Support the sustainable food production and consumption;
3. Support the improvement of animal welfare;
4. Improve the effectiveness, efficiency and reliability of official controls.²⁶

4.1.5 Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP)

The last EU funding programme to name for the purposes of this report is the Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP). Contrarily to the above-named programmes, the SRSP is mainly concerned with assisting reform processes, either institutional, administrative, or growth-enhancing. To this end, the programme provides technical assistance for the full lifecycle of the reform process (preparation, design, implementation). One of its main advantages is that it does not require co-financing by the EU Member States themselves. “The goal is to support Member States’ efforts to design and implement

²³ https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/circular-economy-and-quality-life_en

²⁴ European Commission. 2021. *Single Market Programme* [Fact sheet].

<https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/45590>

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ibid.

resilience-enhancing reforms, thereby contributing to the EU's recovery from the COVID-19 crisis, improving the quality of public services and getting back on the path of sustainable and inclusive growth."²⁷

4.2 Incentives

The transition to the circular economy will demand significant financial resources, both from the public and private sectors and “incentives are vital to overcome barriers stemming from linear models”²⁸. There are several incentives that policy makers may implement with the goal to stimulate circular economy that can benefit investors in the transition process.

Barriers that need to be overcome and that can be targeted by incentives include market failures preventing or delaying circular products, services and solutions, non-pricing of negative externalities, and the steering of markets towards sustainability and promoting behavioural change. “Incentives have the capacity to create value, reduce the risk of investment and improve the competitiveness of value chains that deliver net environmental benefits compared to linear economies.”²⁹

Not all incentives are financial incentives and not all financial incentives are financial instruments targeted at investors to achieve more investment in desirable economic activities and are therefore relevant to this report. These include incentives delivered through blended financial instruments, e.g., financial guarantees or blended finance where public investors take a higher investment risk.

A notable financial incentive instrument are subsidies such as the EU funds discussed above. These incentives aim to encourage private actors, through direct or indirect financial rewards, to gear their behaviour and activities more towards circular economy. Subsidies can transform a circular economy that is not economically viable into a profitable activity. Therefore, subsidies can have a significant and immediate impact, but there is also a risk of market distortion. However, the challenge of scaling needs to be overcome by connecting circular economy projects with commercial financing, given that these projects require co-financing of about three to four times grant amounts.

The correct choice of the right incentive(s) ultimately depends on the addressed market failures. In a report prepared by European Commission on incentives to boost the circular economy, financial instruments are categorised by their market context and calibration:³⁰

²⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/structural-reform-support_en

²⁸ European Commission. 2021. *Incentives to Boost the Circular Economy*.

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/51378e0a-d303-11eb-ac72-01aa75ed71a1>

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Ibid.

Support	High Incentives	Medium Incentives	Low Incentives	No Incentives (Except Rdi & Priority Activities)
Market context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Absent market No financing available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market creation (piloting & demo) Financing not widely available or very expensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market acceleration (scaling up) Financing available but risk (and perception of risk) still persists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mature market. Risk-weighted financing widely available RDI financing absent/expensive
Instruments	Prioritisation instruments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CAPEX grants based on NPV Interest rate/LCV subsidy Longer tenor or grace periods 	Incentivising instruments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No-cost partial guarantees (first loss) Low(er) intensity CAPEX grants CAPEX grant secured against impact Guaranteed residual value 	De-risking instruments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partial concessional co-financing Concessional or waived fees Below market-price guarantees Deferred payment (success fee) Interest rate secured against impact 	For research, development and innovation only <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk capital more appropriate For well-defined priority activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CAPEX grants combined with concessional loans/guarantees
Calibration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To incentivise the uptake of high impact circular technologies and practices Linked to use of proceeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 'Smart' design where the incentives are calibrated to the monetised value of the environmental externalities Linked to the valuation of impact (e.g. level of circularity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To promote systemic transformation by offering support linked to achievement of specific milestones (e.g. with regards to business practices, incorporation of linear and ESG risks into strategies, management tools and investment decisions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prioritisation of technologies/ practices with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ low market adoption ✓ slow uptake ✓ high potential for market transformation

Figure 1. Financial Incentives and Calibration Approach

4.3 Financial Institutions and other For-Profit Initiatives

The circular economy model offers a variety of financing options that go beyond project-related grants. Financial institutions contribute by providing financing and investment for circular economy projects, taking into account the profitability and risks of participation. This economic model helps to protect the environment by avoiding overconsumption, waste and pollution through the reuse of materials, recycling and conversion into raw materials, thus creating a closed production cycle. The implementation of this economic model leads to the emergence of innovative business mechanisms, as well as tools and new ways to assess the risks of the actions undertaken. The financial sector is increasingly demanding these mechanisms, moving away from the old vision of maximising corporate value by increasing share prices and towards a point of view that takes into account social and environmental impacts³¹.

Finance has produced various concepts over the decades. In the 80s and 90s, concepts such as portfolio investment, cost economics and corporate governance, reputation, and

³¹ European Commission. 2019. *Accelerating the Transition to the Circular Economy. Improving access to finance for circular economy projects* [Report].

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/02590134-4548-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>

profitability, among others, gained ground. Nowadays, all these terms have evolved, especially in recent years, with concepts such as impact investment, sustainability, social and ethical investment, climate and responsible finance and green bonds.

Financial institutions are being pushed to participate and invest in circular economy projects in order to achieve the goals set out in the Paris Agreement on climate change. The circular economy system has been introduced over the last five years through various financial instruments such as green bonds, which have helped to accelerate the transition to the new economic model. The main financial instruments are:

- **Green bonds:** Aim to support and finance sustainable and environmentally friendly projects and have the World Bank Group as one of the main issuers. One example: TSKB Green Bond Issue³².
- **Green credits:** Instruments used by banks to finance projects dealing with high levels of pollution in order to reduce the carbon emissions generated, and to finance energy efficiency in order to meet the targets set by the EU. An example of this is the World Bank's US\$ 212.5 loan to VPBank in Vietnam³³.
- **Green Exchanges:** These are aimed at investors who have an interest in investing in and acquiring shares in environmentally friendly companies. This is the case with the Luxembourg Green Exchange, a platform created to contribute to the goals of the Paris Agreement³⁴.
- **Social Bonds:** Debt instruments that focus on financing social and humanitarian projects by helping the neediest communities. Some of the areas where these bonds are used are employment, utilities such as access to drinking water or education. In 2016, Starbucks issued its first US sustainable bond, which has a major impact on society with programmes throughout the coffee supply chain³⁵.

4.3.1 World Bank Group

The World Bank Group (WBG) has increased its recognition regarding Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) in a circular economy. Under the Climate Change Action Plan 2021-2025, which presents significant differences concerning the previous action plan, the WBG aims to find the best way to integrate both waste management and circular economy plans in order to contribute to the development of countries and regions, especially those with high poverty rates, through the implementation of climate change mitigation strategies, and to help meet the Sustainable Development Goals set by the United Nations in the 2030 Agenda. The International Finance Corporation (IFC), as a member of the World Bank Group, contributes by helping countries and regions with limited infrastructure or informal economies, such as Uganda, to strengthen their potential for municipal solid waste management while increasing prosperity through recovery solutions and financing.

The World Bank Group is considered the main source of lending in the area of municipal solid waste management. The World Bank's internal report on an assessment of the World

³² <https://www.tskb.com.tr/uploads/file/tskb-sustainable-finance-framework.pdf>

³³ <https://en.vietnamplus.vn/vpbank-proparco-cooperate-to-promote-green-credit-in-vietnam/185249.vnp>

³⁴ <https://unfccc.int/climate-action/momentum-for-change/financing-for-climate-friendly-investment/luxembourg-green-exchange>

³⁵ <https://stories.starbucks.com/press/2016/starbucks-issues-the-first-u-s-corporate-sustainability-bond/>

Bank Group's support to its client countries indicates a contribution of around \$3 billion over the period 2010 to 2020, representing 10% of the total.³⁶ These figures are higher than those of other multilateral development banks, whose funding for similar activities over the same period ranged from 0.5% to 6.1% of the total.

The following table, which is part of the report for the period 2010-2020, shows that low-income countries receive very little or no share of World Bank loans and investments. Lower-middle-income countries and upper-middle-income countries on the other hand, receive the largest share.

Income Group	World Bank Lending			IFC Investment			IFC Advisory		
	Countries	Commitments		Countries	Commitments		Countries	Commitments	
	(no.)	(US\$, millions)	(%)	(no.)	(US\$, millions)	(%)	(no.)	(US\$, millions)	(%)
HIC	1	22	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
UMIC	11	616	34	4	382	96	11	113	50
LMIC	21	1,145	63	3	16	4	5	92	40
LIC	4	28	15	0	0	0	2	24	10
Total	37	1,811	100	7	398	100	18	229	100

Source: Independent Evaluation Group.

Note: FY - fiscal year; HIC - high-income country; IFC - International Finance Corporation; LIC - low-income country; LMIC - lower-middle-income country; UMIC - upper-middle-income country.

Figure 2. World Bank Group Municipal Solid Waste Management Operations by Country Income Group.

The World Bank is the world's largest international organisation for financing developing countries and has the best triple-A rating. The World Bank not only provides loans, but also offers advice and expertise on a wide range of topics such as climate or human capital. It is integrated into five international organisations, each with a specific purpose. These include the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD), the International Development Association (IDA), the International Finance Corporation (IFC), the Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA) and the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID).

4.3.2 European Investment Bank (EIB)

Of all financial institutions, the European Investment Bank (EIB) is the largest multilateral financial institution in the world. It provides financial support and advice to meet the needs of businesses in areas such as climate, cohesion, innovation, SMEs and sustainability in relation to circular economy projects inside and outside the EU that aim to prevent waste through reuse, recycling and regeneration of natural systems³⁷. These projects are implemented through the European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI)³⁸, which aims to increase economic growth in the long term and improve competitiveness within the EU

³⁶ World Bank. 2022. *Annual Report 2022. Helping Countries Adapt to a Changing World*. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/37972/AR2022EN.pdf>

³⁷ <https://www.eib.org/en/about/at-a-glance/index.htm>

³⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/economy-works-people/european-fund-strategic-investments_en

through private investment. There is also EU funding for innovators (InnovFin), which aims to help small businesses access finance by supporting projects³⁹.

As mentioned above, the EIB provides not only financial support but also advisory services to help identify the best way to improve the financial viability of projects related to the circular economy. A large number of projects in many different sectors have benefited from these investments, with a total financing agreement of €65,15 billion in 2022⁴⁰. Broken down by sector, the results for the period 2015-2019 are as follows⁴¹:

Sector	Lending (€ millions)	Share
Industry and services	747	30%
Waste management	594	24%
Agriculture and bioeconomy	438	18%
Water management	426	17%
Mobility	95	4%
Urban development	80	3%
Energy	71	3%
Total	2,452	100%

Figure 3. EIB Circular Economy Signed Operations, 2015-2019

The EIB Group claims to be constantly adapting to new opportunities and emerging market needs and is working with SMEs to support them to develop new financing projects. InnovFin Advisory coordinated the launch of the European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECBF), a venture fund designed to help growth companies with a focus on the circular economy and high innovation potential to contribute to Europe's environmental goals by 2050. The €300 million fund will invest in companies across a range of sectors, including the blue economy and fisheries, agri-food, industrial biotechnology, biotech chemicals and materials, packaging, and household and personal care products⁴². All EIB financing and advisory services are provided primarily through InnovFin Advisory and the European Investment Advisory Hub (EIAH).

4.3.3 Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE)

Given the importance of the circular economy in combating climate change and the various programmes designed to help businesses achieve the agreed targets, the Joint Initiative on the Circular Economy (JICE) brought together the EIB and five European promotional banks: Bank Gospodarstwa Krajowego (BGK – Poland), the Caisse des Dépôts Groupe (CDC – France) including Bpifrance and Banque des Territoires, Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP – Italy), the European Investment Bank (EIB), Instituto de Crédito Oficial (ICO – Spain) and KfW – Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (Germany). This five-year plan (2019-2023) aims to accelerate the transition to a circular economy by providing up to €10 billion in loans,

³⁹ <https://www.eib.org/en/products/advisory-services/innovfin-advisory/index.htm>

⁴⁰ <https://www.eib.org/en/about/key-figures/index.htm>

⁴¹ <https://www.eib.org/en/publications/the-eib-in-the-circular-economy-guide>

⁴² <https://www.ecbf.vc/investment-focus>

financing, technical assistance and guarantees for appropriate circular economy projects by 2023.⁴³

The sectors that the JICE supports are diverse and include several companies and projects such as water management (AQUASERVICE – Spain), waste (STARMEAT – Poland), urban development (PALAZZO DELLE FINANZE – Italy), services (VESTIAIRE COLLECTIVE – France) and other sectors such as agriculture, industry and mobility.

4.3.4 European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)

The last financial institution to be mentioned at European level is the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD). This institution was founded to rebuild Central and Eastern Europe after the Cold War. The EBRD is committed to promoting market-oriented economies and developing private and entrepreneurial initiatives. It launched its first circular economy plan, called the Circular Economy Regional Initiative, in Turkey and the Western Balkans in 2021 to address the barriers preventing the transition to a circular economy with a focus on SMEs. Funding is also provided with support from the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and technical cooperation from the Austrian Federal Ministry of Finance, amounting to \$13.76 million and \$1 million respectively.

The global economy has an enormous impact on the environment and this programme aims to change the way raw materials are used, from extraction to disposal. It will be necessary to improve the management of raw materials throughout their life cycle, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, especially CO₂ emissions, divert waste from landfills and oceans, and eliminate, avoid or better manage harmful chemicals⁴⁴.

4.4 Asset Management Firms

Investments in the circular economy are a matter of interest to all types of companies like large asset management companies, governments, SMEs, and financial institutions. According to a study by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, during the period comprised between December 2019 and December 2021, the amount of corporate and sovereign bonds that were issued annually experienced an increase of five times to the first period.⁴⁵ There are new and better investment opportunities for all sectors when shifting to a circular economy that contributes to the prosperity of the companies besides controlling environmental impact. The private sector is each time more attracted to the new opportunities that this economy model offers, the contribution to the transition into a carbon-neutral economy, and the fact of having a healthy portfolio.

Among the top three largest asset management firms we stand out BlackRock, Vanguard Group, and Fidelity investments. Focusing on the first one, BlackRock launched a Circular Economy Fund with a number of total assets that amounted to \$1.9 trillion. Of those assets, at least 80% were invested in equity securities of companies worldwide, like Adidas, which benefit or contribute towards the transition to a circular economy. Under normal market

⁴³ <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2019-191-eur-10-billion-to-support-the-circular-economy-in-the-eu>

⁴⁴ <https://www.ebrd.com/news/2021/ebrd-launches-first-circulareconomy-programme.html>

⁴⁵ <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/finance/overview>

conditions, the fund will invest in a portfolio of equity securities of companies rated on their ability to manage risks and opportunities associated with circular economy and other key points such as environmental, social, and governance issues (ESG).⁴⁶

Another example of circular finance is Intesa Sanpaolo, the leading bank in Italy and one of the top banks in Europe with more than 14 million customers. The transition is seen as a chance to create value and achieve sustainable economic development both with a social and environmental impact. From 2007 to 2014, the contribution to renewable energies and the environment amounted to €11 billion. The business plan of Intesa Sanpaolo for 2018-2021 includes among its topics the relevance of the circular economy to fight climate change and other issues such as waste, pollution, and biodiversity loss.⁴⁷

4.5 Crowdfunding

A recently introduced concept, crowdfunding has proven a legitimate way to collect the necessary funds for an initiative, project or product. It consists of 1) the product's owner, who digitally promotes it in the 2) crowdfunding platform, in order to find 3) people willing to provide the financial resources needed to realise the owner's product. Due to the fact that it is a relatively new funding strategy, no formal institutions are involved in the process, therefore it is considered an alternative form of financing. Although it is a fairly new concept, the volume of funds raised through crowdfunding platforms is expected to reach \$57 billion in 2022 and \$90 billion in 2025.⁴⁸

The main difference between crowdfunding and other traditional funding strategies is the number of contributors and the scale of their contributions. Where traditional funding comes from a small number of sources in sizeable amounts, crowdfunding engages numerous sources in smaller contributions. Thus, crowdfunding can mostly or entirely fund small initiatives, but will only constitute a part of the capital in case of larger projects.

As an advantage, crowdfunding can constitute not only the form of funding, but also a way of promoting and creating awareness for the initiative in question. Since, through the platform, it can reach an extensive audience, their contribution to the project can also be considered its validation and, if the project reaches their amount goal quickly, its market potential. Even if, in this case, financial institutions may be willing to invest in the project, crowdfunding still presents the setback that, due to its lack of regulation, crowdfunding can be seen by non-reliable by institutionalised funders.

Crowdfunding can be peer-to-peer tending, where a crowdfunding campaign is posted online, and different contributors provide their donations. But it can also be reward-based, where the owner of the product or service sets up different "rewards" depending on the funder's contribution (for example, a tier system can be set up and the funders will receive from the most basic to the most elaborate version of the product they funded). Finally,

⁴⁶ <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-examples/the-worlds-largest-investor-embraces-the-circular-economy-blackrock>

⁴⁷ <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-examples/embracing-the-circular-economy-at-italys-largest-bank-intesa-sanpaolo>

⁴⁸ <https://www.isbank.com.tr/blog/kitlesel-fonlama-nedir>

crowdfunding may be equity-based, where funders will receive the amount they contributed to company shares.

Besides, it is widely accepted that crowdfunding can deliver a business with more than just money to invest. Leone et al. in a study focused on reward-based crowdfunding showed that it can also be a source of some non-monetary benefits such as validation of the business idea, definition of the product/service (through customer feedback), product promotion, innovation or identification of internationalization opportunity among others. Furthermore, this type of crowdfunding shapes circular business models in informational mechanisms, innovation networking and marketing aspects; and it can reduce risks connected to the circular business model.⁴⁹

Multiple crowdfunding platforms are readily available and well-known to the public, such as Kickstarter and GoFundMe. In addition to these, the European Crowdfunding Network exists, where professional training and transparent digital financing opportunities are offered.⁵⁰⁵¹

A success case of circular business model foundation through crowdfunding (Kickstarter platform) is Vesica Piscis. It is a small enterprise created in Elx, Spain, and mainly specialized in footwear. Their business model is based on circular economy and respect to the environment. Their campaign was launched at the beginning of December 2015, using rewards as pairs of shoes, and aiming to obtain 15.000 euros in one year. In June 2016, the project reached 17.589 € allowing them to launch the creation of their business.⁵²

⁴⁹ Leone, D., Cristina Pietronudo, M., Gabteni, H., & Rosaria Carli, M. (2023). *Reward-based crowdfunding for building a valuable circular business model*. Journal of Business Research, 157.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113562>

⁵⁰ <https://eurocrowd.org>

⁵¹ <https://eurocrowd.org>

⁵² Leone, D., Cristina Pietronudo, M., Gabteni, H., & Rosaria Carli, M. (2023). *Reward-based crowdfunding for building a valuable circular business model*. Journal of Business Research, 157.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113562>

5. Green Public Procurement

Defined as “a process whereby public authorities seek to procure goods, services and works that have a lower environmental impact throughout their life cycle than goods, services and works with the same primary function that would otherwise be procured”⁵³, Green Public Procurement (GPP) can also constitute a valuable tool to encourage the circular economy. The public sector’s spending comprises around 14% of the EU’s gross domestic product and, with such a significant purchasing power, their choice of greener products and services could mean an important change towards more sustainable production and consumption⁵⁴.

On the one hand, GPP has the potential of modifying the marketing. Through GPP, public authorities can encourage various industries to produce greener products and services. Due to the nature of the services public authorities purchase (transport, construction, health services, education), GPP could have a great infrastructural impact. On the other, GPP remains a voluntary initiative and states can choose to what extent they implement it. Barriers to further introduce it are a lack of political support, perception that green products are more costly, the lack of consistent criteria evaluating which products are more environmentally friendly, the low co-operation between public authorities or the lack of training of staff responsible.

Today, 22 European countries (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain and Sweden) have adopted National Action Plans for GPP and started to build their implementation infrastructures under the EU Public Procurement Directive 2014/24/EU. Five EU countries do not have a National Action Plan in force (anymore): Estonia, Hungary, Luxembourg, Romania and Slovenia.⁵⁵

With respect to GPP in Spain and in accordance with the provisions of Article 202 of Law 9/2017, of 8 November on Public Sector Contracts, The Murcia regional development agency INFO states in its specifications and in its contracts, special conditions of execution of an environmental and “green” nature, whenever its link with the object of the contract is possible. This applies more precisely in some furniture supply contracts for participation in fairs, travel agency service contracts, audit service contracts, consultancy contracts, IT support service contracts, etc.

Failure to comply with these conditions may entail for the contractor the penalties established in the specific administrative clauses that govern that range of contracts.

5.1 EU GPP Food Catering Services and Vending Machines Criteria

The EC has developed GPP criteria for specific sectors to facilitate the inclusion of environmentally friendly requirements. GPP criteria are to be understood as part of the procurement process and must comply with its standard format and rules as set out in the

⁵³ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/what_en.htm

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/action_plan_en.htm

Public Procurement Directive 2014/24/EU (public works, supply and service contracts). Therefore, the EU GPP criteria must comply with the following principles: Free movement of goods and services and freedom of establishment; non-discrimination and equal treatment; transparency; proportionality and mutual recognition. The specific sectors for which criteria are set are:

- Cleaning products and services, computers, monitors, tablets and smartphones,
- Data centres, server rooms and cloud services,
- Electricity,
- Food Catering services and vending machines,
- Furniture,
- Imaging Equipment, consumables, and print services,
- Office Building Design,
- Construction and Management,
- Paints, varnishes and road markings,
- Public Space Maintenance,
- Road Design, Construction and Maintenance,
- Road lighting and traffic signals,
- Textiles,
- Road Transport

The food and catering industry can impact the environment at all its production stages, and the EC aimed to address the key environmental impacts of the food and catering industry and provide various approaches to minimise these. The EC divides the criteria in the different steps of food, catering services and vending machine procurement:

- The selection criteria, where the public authorities would evaluate the service tenderer (and not the specific product yet), like the verification of a catering service's experience in sustainable catering;
- The technical specifications, constituting what the public authorities would require of the tenderers in the context of the service requested, such as the monitoring that the product offered is organic;
- The contract performance clauses, defining how the agreement between the public authorities and the tenderer are going to be carried out, an example being the assurance that tap water and reusable cups are provided during the service;
- And the award criteria, where the public authority considers the quality of the tenders and compares costs, such as the consideration of those tenderers offering a minimum percentage of organic products.⁵⁶

The criteria are voluntary and presented in two scales of specificity: Core criteria, focusing on the most essential factors for an easy and cost-effective application of GPP; and

⁵⁶ Neto, Belmira et al. 2016. *Revision of the EU Green Public Procurement Criteria for Food and Catering Services*. JRC Science for Policy Report
<https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/from-crm/9.%20Revision%20of%20the%20EU%20Green%20Public%20Procurement%20Criteria%20for%20Food%20and%20Catering%20Services.pdf>

comprehensive criteria, which accounts for more aspects of environmental performance for those public authorities whose priority is green purchasing⁵⁷.

According to the Food Catering services and vending machines GPP Criteria⁵⁸, this product group includes direct procurement of food by public authorities and procurement of catering services, either using their own resources or facilities or through full or partial outsourcing via catering companies. Food may be sourced directly from producers, manufacturers, wholesalers or importers, or may be part of the service provided by catering companies. In the same document, several key environmental impacts are identified below with their solutions according to the EU GPP approach to minimise these impacts.

Key Environmental Impacts	EU GPP Approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy used in farming, agricultural activities, food processing and facilities • Land use and land-use change (e.g. destruction of natural habitats, particularly forests and related CO2 emissions associated with the production of feed, crops, fruits, vegetable fats, etc.) • Depletion of fish stocks and reduction of biodiversity • Production and use of fertilisers and pesticides • Water use and water pollution • Emissions of pollutants such as methane or nitrites from farming and agricultural activities • Disposal of waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic food products • More environmentally responsible marine and aquaculture food products • Increased offer of plant-based menus • More environmentally responsible vegetable fats • Food and beverage waste prevention • Other waste: prevention, sorting and disposal • Energy and water consumption in kitchen

Figure 4. (SWD) EU GPP Criteria for food, catering services and vending machines

⁵⁷ SWD(2019) 366 final. 2019. *EU green public procurement criteria for food, catering services and vending machines*. European Commission.
[https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/190927_EU_GPP_criteria_for_food_and_catering_services_SWD_\(2019\)_366_final.pdf](https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/190927_EU_GPP_criteria_for_food_and_catering_services_SWD_(2019)_366_final.pdf)

⁵⁸ Ibid.

6. Public Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

In this section, specific public financing schemes in the Region of Murcia are to be described; including grant programmes from the Regional Governmental administration (CARM) and the Regional Development Institute (INFO).

6.1 INFO

The main objective of INFO is to promote regional economic growth and competitiveness in the Region of Murcia by promoting the economy, increasing investment, removing obstacles and establishing an environment that favours competitiveness. With the aim of guaranteeing enhanced development and economic growth amongst regional SMEs.

6.1.1 Grant programme for energy efficiency actions in SMEs and large companies in the industrial sector⁵⁹

Objective: Help the industrial sector in the incorporation of energy efficient technology and the implementation of control systems.

Industry is an intensive sector in energy consumption and, therefore, the efficient and optimised use of such energy is a major factor of competitiveness, so that actions aimed at improving energy efficiency have a very important impact on such competitiveness.

Despite the fact that companies have already been making numerous investment efforts in energy matters, there is still a large margin for reducing final energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions.

The incorporation of the best available technologies in equipment and processes and the implementation of energy management systems are the two basic mechanisms for improving energy efficiency.

To this end, the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism published Royal Decree 263/2019, of 12 April, which regulates the grant programme with multi-regional ERDF means for energy efficiency actions in SMEs and large companies in the industrial sector. This decree established a mechanism of direct concession to the different Autonomous Communities and called for the publication of an order regulating the grants for the industrial sector.

Three calls have been made in the Region of Murcia since the region was entrusted by IDEA to manage the multi-regional ERDF means for grants to SMEs and large companies in energy efficiency.

⁵⁹ <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/web/portal/eficiencia-energetica>

Of the 106 dossiers presented by as many industrial companies in the Region of Murcia, 73 dossiers have been approved with a subsidy of €10,5 million, 55% of the grant going to SMEs and the remaining 45% to large companies.

6.1.2 CHIS grant line for the calculation and certification of carbon footprint in organisation/product and water footprint⁶⁰

Objective: Programme aimed at encouraging and promoting innovative measures of companies through their climate responsibility and sustainability. The aim is to improve the competitive position of companies and promote business innovation in two types of corporate social responsibility measures, specifically the calculation of the carbon footprint of organisations and products as well as the water footprint of companies.

SMEs may be beneficiaries of the grants contemplated in this programme.

Types of eligible services for the promotion of business innovation through corporate responsibility and climate sustainability:

- Organisational and product carbon footprint (ISO 14064 and 14067);
- Corporate water footprint (ISO 14046);
- Two open calls in 2022 with 180 SME applicants and a grant budget of €200,000.

6.1.3 Innovation voucher for optimising industrial processes and products eco-innovation⁶¹

Objective: Programme aimed at encouraging and promoting both product design and process improvement for boosting sustainability in regional enterprises. The aim is to improve the competitive position of companies and promote business innovation.

Beneficiaries: SMEs located in the Region of Murcia.

Types of eligible services:

- Optimisation of industrial processes;
- Product design (eco-innovation).

One call opened in 2021 with 19 SME applicants. A total of 9 SMEs were financed with a total budget of €81,000. Another call opened in 2019 with 41 SME applicants. A total of 19 SMEs were financed with a total budget of €167,000.

6.1.4 R&D support to regional technological centres for developing sustainable products and processes⁶²

Objective: Programme aimed at encouraging and promoting non-economic research and technological development of products and processes, including knowledge and technology transfer to enterprises. The final aim is to improve the competitive position of companies and promote business innovation.

⁶⁰ <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/web/portal/sostenibilidadempresarial>

⁶¹ <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/cheques-de-innovacion>

⁶² <https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es>

Beneficiaries: Technology centres located in the Region of Murcia.

Types of eligible services:

- Non-economic research & technological development;
- Knowledge and technology activities for wide dissemination of R&D results.

One call opened in 2022 aimed at 9 technological centre applicants with a total budget of €4,4 million that financed 46 projects.

6.1.5 R&D support to enterprises for developing sustainable products and processes⁶³

Objective: Programme aimed at encouraging and promoting research and technological development of products and processes. The final aim is to improve the competitive position of companies and promote business innovation.

Beneficiaries: Enterprises located in the Region of Murcia.

Types of eligible services:

- Research & technological development

One call opened in 2020 with a total budget of €6,000,000 that financed 53 projects.

6.2 CARM

6.2.1 Grants to the operational funds of fruit and vegetable producer organisations (OPFH)

Objective: To establish and carry out administrative and on-the-spot checks on applications for financial aid to fruit and vegetable producer organisations based in the Region of Murcia and to grant the aid accepted.

Beneficiaries: Companies and other entities.

6.2.2 Grants for investments in energy efficiency and renewable energies (biogas and agricultural biomass).

Objective: Actions to the energy valorisation of manures and agricultural biomass:

- Investments in small-capacity biogas plants.
- Investments related to agricultural biomass management for final energy use.

Beneficiaries: Citizens and companies and other entities. The beneficiaries are natural or legal entities, having the status of private company being owners of an agricultural or livestock holding.

⁶³ Ibid.

6.2.3 Grants for innovation projects in rural areas

Objective: Grant and process the payment of aid for the creation and operation of operational groups of the European Innovation Association in terms of productivity and Agricultural Sustainability, corresponding to measure 16.1 of the Rural Development Program of the Region of Murcia 2014-2020.

Beneficiaries: Companies and other Entities. Associations registered in the Register of Associations of the Region of Murcia.

6.2.4 Grants for investments in farms

Objective: Grant aid, in the form of a subsidy and on a competitive bidding basis, to those professional farmers who make investments in farms (code 3014).

The aid will take the form of reimbursement of actual costs, in accordance with article 67 of Regulation (EU) No. 1303/2013.

The intensity of the aid will be 40% of the admissible amount of the generally eligible investments included in the aid application. This amount will increase by an additional 20 percentage points, in the case of investments in farms located in mountainous areas of the Region of Murcia (Annex II), and another 20% additional, in the case of young farmers who have established themselves during the five years prior to the application for aid, and continue to meet the age condition (under 41 years of age).

The maximum admissible number of investments, per beneficiary and holding, is limited to €60,000.

Beneficiaries: Companies and other Entities; and Citizenship, owners of agricultural holdings who comply with the figure of professional farmer and who make investments in their holding.

6.2.5 Grants for investments in farms linked to the creation of agricultural companies

Objective: Grant aid, in the form of a subsidy and on a competitive basis, to those young people who make investments in agricultural holdings, simultaneously with aid for the creation of agricultural companies.

Beneficiaries: Young Citizenship

6.2.6 Grants for investment in processing, marketing and development of agricultural products

Objective: Granting aids for investments in the processing, marketing and development of agricultural products.

Beneficiaries: Citizens and companies and other entities. Individuals or legal entities and communities of property whose workplaces are located in the Region of Murcia.

6.2.7 Grants for the programme for the application of precision agriculture and 4.0 technologies in the agricultural and livestock sector, as part of the Plan to boost the sustainability and competitiveness of agriculture and livestock farming

Objective: Call for aids for the implementation of equipment or adaptation of existing equipment to precision agriculture in agricultural holdings, aimed at meeting the objectives of the Green Pact in the agricultural sector.

Beneficiaries: Citizens and Companies and other Entities.

- Natural or legal persons, of a private or public nature, who are owners of livestock farms, provided that they are considered SMEs.
- In the case of collective investments, groups of natural or legal persons, of a private or public nature, or without their own personality in accordance with the terms of Article 67.2 of Royal Decree-Law 36/2020, of 30 December, and any organisation or association of producers recognised by the competent authority, comprising a minimum of five owners of farms, provided that they are considered SMEs.

6.2.8 Grants for the consolidation of irrigation by using reclaimed water from wastewater reservoirs

Objective: To grant aid for the consolidation of pre-existing irrigation systems in irrigation communities through the execution of new works, installations, devices and equipment that enable the incorporation and use in irrigation areas of reclaimed water from wastewater treatment plants.

Beneficiaries: Companies and other entities. Irrigation communities are attached to the basin organisation of the Segura Hydrographic Demarcation whose irrigation area is located mainly (more than 50 %) in the Region of Murcia and on which the financial burden of the investments and expenses considered eligible falls.

6.2.9 Grant for the improvement of energy efficiency and renewable energy generation in irrigation communities. EURI Funds – RDP 2014-2020

Objective: Call 2022 with EURI funds for grants to improve energy efficiency and renewable energy generation in irrigation communities and general irrigation communities in the Region of Murcia.

Beneficiaries: Companies and other entities. Irrigation communities and general irrigation communities – user communities regulated in Chapter IV of the Consolidated Text of the Water Law approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2001, of 20 July and in Chapter IV of the Public Hydraulic Domain Regulations approved by Royal Decree 849/1986, of 11 April.

7. Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

Two different private financial schemes are considered in this section. First, private financial schemes from bank and financial cooperatives are described. Secondly, some alternative non-bank based financial schemes are detailed.

7.1 Bank and Financial Cooperatives Schemes

The Bank of Spain has shown its concern regarding sustainable economy by prioritising in its research agenda an analysis of the multiple implications that climate change and the transition towards a more sustainable growth model have for the economy as a whole and for the financial system. This is reflected in the last report of analytical and research priorities for 2020-2024⁶⁴. Among the long-term trends of the Spanish economy, it prioritises the study of the informative content on sustainability and the degree of compliance with the recommendations on climate risk included in corporate reports, as well as the incorporation of sustainability factors in public debt markets, in portfolio management and in the conduct of monetary policy.

According to the Regional Statistics Center of Murcia, in 2022, 25 different credit institutions operated in the Region, including credit cooperatives and banks. Together, totalled to 520 branches, from which 187 are based in Murcia city, and 76 in Cartagena, the two most populated cities in the Region. On one hand, the most representative entity among banks is Caixabank, with 167 branches; and on the other hand Cajamar Group, with 113 branches, within credit cooperatives.

The Cajamar Cooperative Group has always worked with an eye on local development and, undoubtedly, the agri-food sector is its most intense field of action. Their main commitment has been to give their best to the field, to all the companies in the sector and to its auxiliary industry. In this way, the trajectory has been parallel to that of those areas in which they have had a commercial presence. And thus they have made the agri-food culture their own. Their DNA is an agro-DNA. The agri-food sector represents a high percentage of their total activity, and therefore, they have developed their own structure (internal and external), recognising the role of the economic sector as a pillar of the maintenance and development of the entity. In this sector there are many elements that differentiate them from other entities:

- A wide range of specific products and services;
- Their commitment to research and innovation in production systems;
- And the dissemination of knowledge among farmers and managers in the auxiliary industry.

⁶⁴ Banco de España. 2021. *Prioridades analíticas y de investigación del Banco de España 2020-2024*. https://www.bde.es/f/webbde/INF/MenuVertical/AnalisisEconomico/Actualizacion_2021_Prioridades_analitic as_BE.pdf

For them, providing support and quality service to farmers is essential, regardless of the volume. And to the companies that bring together cooperation and channel their prosperity as well. This is the case with cooperatives, which for years have made possible that the effort of the farmer has a reflection with a lot of specific weight in all corners of Spain and numerous countries of the European Community.

The Ethics and CSR Management Committee of Banco de Crédito Cooperativo, head of Grupo Cooperativo Cajamar, ratifies and promotes its commitment to the social, economic, and sustainable environment in which it interacts. Hence, although the very nature of its activity generates a minimal environmental impact, it has committed to sustainable development within its business model that contemplates not only direct impacts, but also indirect ones generated through the consequences of its financing activities, asset management and the management of its supply chain.

Cajamar Cooperative Group's mission is to contribute with financial solutions to the economic development and social progress of its members, clients, and the environment in which the group operates through a unique strategy based on the principle of cooperation, social economy, and sustainable development.

Their vision is being the market leader in cooperative banking and a reference for the agri-sector in Spain, recognised for its strength, commitment, and high ethical standards in relation to their customers, members, employees, and the environment in which they operate, based on a sustainable model.

Their purpose is to continue ensuring people's well-being and social progress, by cooperating to generate ideas and innovation that contribute to sustainable connectedness of territories.

The cooperative banking model brings diversity to the banking system: It truly contributes to local sustainable development, generates a stable and lasting relationship with the environment, reduces the risks associated with speculation and the generation of bubbles through a countercyclical business model, contributes to reducing the risks associated with the usual banking model: moral hazard, adverse selection, and asymmetric information.

Their main objectives:

- To adapt to regulatory expectations, which encompass compliance with the EU action plan for sustainable finance and adaptation to important regulatory changes in disclosure and management of environmental risks;
- To expand the products and services catalogue that include ESG criteria (Environmental, Social and Governance), responding to demand of individuals and companies and taking advantage of financing opportunities that will arise in the transition towards low carbon economy;
- To advance in climate and environmental risk management through the implementation of climate indicators in the risk methodology and manuals, and developments in carbonisation analysis process of the portfolio;
- To develop and implement an internal training plan in sustainable finance to strengthen the presence of values related to sustainability in the group's culture.

- Continue reinforcing the presence of sustainability and the consolidation of ESG criteria in the group's strategy and governance.

CaixaBank is a highly representative entity in the region. It has an environmental and climate strategy whose objective is to contribute to the transition towards sustainability by financing and investing in sustainable projects, environmental and climate risk management, and the reduction of direct impact of our operations. Within this strategy, CaixaBank includes financial lines like:

- Loans linked to sustainability variables which are loans linked to ESG (Environmental, Social and Corporate Governance) criteria (€10,832 million mobilised through the 92 loans made available in 2021);
- Green loans: These are loans with a positive environmental impact, whose underlying are eligible projects or assets, in areas such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable transport, emission reduction, waste treatment and sustainable building, which comply with the Green Loan Principles (GLP) issued by the Loan Market Association (€1,625 million mobilised in 36 green loans in 2021).
- Eco-financing: Encouraging sustainable investments that use resources more efficiently and/or reduce environmental impacts. To do this, they offer personal eco-loans and eco-microloans to finance the purchase of efficient vehicles and household appliances and home renovations to improve energy efficiency. And also financing projects related to efficient water use, renewable energies, waste management, energy efficiency, ecological agriculture and rural development, through eco-financing lines for the agricultural sector (€61 million made available through 919 loans linked to eco-financing lines in 2021).

Banco Sabadell is also among the most represented entities in the region of Murcia. It has impulse different projects towards circular economy (Givers, W3R, Ding Dong project or B-COME). Banco Sabadell is committed to sustainability, and it has established a commitment to sustainability, a framework for action that ensures the integration into a strategy of a forward-looking vision in relation to environmental, social and governance (ESG) commitments, that aligns its business objectives with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and that establishes action levers to generate transformation and promotion activities. To do this, it has brought on board all of the institution's corporate bodies and established four strategic pillars:

- Progress as a sustainable institution;
- Support customers in the transition to a sustainable economy;
- Offer investment opportunities that contribute to sustainability;
- Work together for a sustainable and cohesive society.

Banco Santander is another bank entity which has reinforced its commitment to the circular economy by converting its cards into street furniture. It also has implemented subsidies and grants for sustainability such aids for energy efficiency, self-consumption aid or moves plan.⁶⁵

⁶⁵ <https://www.bancosantander.es/en/santander-sostenible/ayudas-subsvenciones-verdes>

Withing other entities with presence in Murcia it is worth mentioning BBVA which presents a wide portfolio of funds for investing in sustainable assets. Other programs and sustainable financial lines can be consulted on the following websites.

Bancofar	https://www.bancofar.es/documents/sostenibilidad
Bankinter	https://www.bankinter.com/empresas/financiacion
BBVA	https://www.bbva.es/general/sostenibilidad/soluciones-para-negocios.html?int=banndesthomep-landcampssoste
CaixaBank	https://www.caixabank.com/es/sostenibilidad/transicion-sostenible/negocio-sostenible.html
Caja Rural Central	https://www.ruralcentral.es/es/sostenibilidad
Caja Rural de Granada	https://www.cajaruralgranada.es/es/autonomos/lineas-inversion
Cajamar	https://www.bcc.es/es/responsabilidad-corporativa/gestion-ambiental
Deutsche Bank	https://country.db.com/spain/sostenibilidad
Ibercaja	https://www.ibercaja.es/empresas/soluciones/empresas / https://www.ibercaja.com/sostenibilidad/compromisos-con-el-medio-ambiente/iniciativas-medioambientales
ING	https://www.ing.es/sobre-ing/banca-responsable/planeta#
Kutxabank	https://www.kutxabank.com/sostenibilidad
Renta 4	https://www.r4.com/que-necesitas/compromiso-social/inversion-sostenible
Sabadell	https://bancsabadell.com/cs/Satellite/SabAtl/PYMEs/1191332199861/es/
Santander	https://www.bancosantander.es/santander-sostenible/ayudas-subsvenciones-verdes

7.2 Alternative Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

In Murcia one can find alternatives to bank-financing schemes. Some of them are described in the table below.

<u>Alternative Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia</u>	
<u>ICREF lines</u>	
ICREF+AGRO	
Aim	Financing self-employed and companies in the agricultural and agri-food sector to improve the fluidity of credit, thus being able to serve the modernisation and innovation of these sectors, and that can also contribute to the maintenance and creation of employment, also offering the personal guarantee for 100 % of the amount of the loan by AVALAM S.G.R.

Target	Self-employed and companies in the agricultural sector (agriculture, livestock and fishing) and agri-food (food and beverage companies)
Financial magnitude	Total financing scheme: €12 million (€6 million Financial Entities + €6 million ICREF)
ICREF financia 100	
Aim	Financing the self-employed, entrepreneurs and micro-enterprises to undertake their business projects, allowing them to consolidate and even increase their market share, also offering a personal guarantee for 100% of the loan amount from AVALAM S.G.R.
Target	Self-employed and SMEs
Financial magnitude	€6 million (€3 million Financial Entities + €3 million ICREF)
AVALAM lines	
AVALAM industrial support line	
Aim	Investment and working capital linked to the growth or start-up of the SME. CERSA, through the Ministry of Industry, Commerce and Tourism, subsidises opening, study and guarantee commissions at zero cost and reduces the interest rate to 1.80%.
Target	SMEs whose activity is carried out in the industrial, manufacturing and services to industry sectors. SMEs with a legal nature that make an industrial investment, even if they are not industries.
Financial magnitude	Up to €600,000
AQUISGRAN	
Aim	AQUISGRAN is a new line of non-bank business financing that is channelled exclusively in the region of Murcia through AVALAM without the intervention of a financial institution. This is a pioneering formula in Spain to promote access to credit for SMEs and the self-employed in an agile and direct manner.
Target	SMEs and freelancers with headquarters in the Region of Murcia
Financial magnitude	Investment: maximum €300,000. Up to 7 years and up to 12 months of optional grace period. Current: maximum €300,000. Up to 5 years and up to 12 months of optional grace period. Entrepreneurs: maximum €50,000. Up to 5 years and up to 12 months of optional grace period.
CRECE	
Aim	Investment in fixed assets for the business such as machinery, facilities, means of transportation, reforms of the facilities, acquisition of real estate, etc.
Target	SMEs and freelancers belonging to sectors not excluded from this aid: Companies operating in the real estate sector, companies without staff, companies in crisis, companies that do not comply with the legislative requirements in social, labour, ethical and environmental matters that are applicable at all times, companies and organizations dependent on or owned by the State, Autonomous and Local Public Administration.

Financial magnitude	Up to €600,000
INFO Grants	
INFO grants to create or maintain employment	
Aim	The grant program is aimed at those companies that have the initiative to create employment or maintain employment and that carry out a training workshop that contributes to their transition towards the green economy or their digital transformation, depending on the type of subsidy requested.
Target	<p>a) Those micro-enterprises and self-employed workers that carry out their activity in the territorial scope of the Region of Murcia, which have at least one work centre open in said territory, which have between one and nine salaried workers and a turnover or balance less than two million euros.</p> <p>b) Cooperatives and labour companies that carry out their business activity in the territorial scope of the Region of Murcia that have at least one open workplace in said territory. In the case of cooperatives, they must have opted for the modality of assimilated to employed persons, for the purposes of Social Security.</p>
Financial magnitude	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aid for job creation: €5,000 • Aid to maintain employment: €3000
INFO Call for Energy Efficiency Actions	
Aim	Program aimed at encouraging and promoting actions in SMEs and large companies in the industrial sector that reduce carbon dioxide emissions and final energy consumption, by improving energy efficiency, thereby helping to achieve reduction targets of final energy consumption set by Directive 2012/27/EU, of the European Parliament and of the Council, of October 25, 2012, on energy efficiency
Target	Companies that are considered SMEs or large companies in the industrial sector, whose CNAE 2009 is between 07 and 33 and 35 to 39 and energy service companies.
Financial magnitude	<p>The amount of the aid will be the lesser of the following three:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 30% of the eligible investment of the project. 2. The maximum amount that, depending on the region where the project is located and type of promoting company: 35% (large company), 45% (medium) and 55% (small) 3. The maximum amount established in the corresponding call.

8. Financing Schemes & Agro2Circular Business Models

Food production processes are becoming increasingly intensive in energy, land, and water consumption, posing significant pressure on global planetary boundaries.⁶⁶ In particular, intensive agricultural practices are responsible for one-third of global terrestrial acidification⁶⁷ and 80% of global deforestation.⁶⁸ The agri-food sector is also one of the highest contributors to climate change, releasing between 21 and 37% of total GHG emissions.⁶⁹ In Europe, food production is responsible for 30% of GHG emissions.⁷⁰ Additionally, the environmental costs of food production are further exacerbated by high losses across the supply chain, accounting for about 20% of the food globally produced.⁷¹ Furthermore, a significant amount of multilayer plastic films is used as industrial packaging for the protection of food and agriculture for crops, and only a low share of it is sorted and recycled in Europe.⁷² This is due to several reasons, including the lack of sorting and recycling technologies and the unavailability of financially and environmentally sustainable models for the valorisation of this type of waste. Most of this waste is indeed landfilled or incinerated, generating a relevant environmental burden and a loss of economic value.

In this context, the application of circular economy principles in the agri-food sector constitutes a great opportunity to reduce its environmental impacts and develop more sustainable food systems, enabling the transition towards resource-efficient production modes.⁷³ The transition from a linear to a circular economy requires not only the adoption of new products, technologies and processes, but also of innovative business models that find new ways to generate value for companies and society contributing to sustainability, efficiency and productivity.⁷⁴ This chapter aims to explore the concept of circular business model in the context of Agro2Circular project and clarify its relation with the financing schemes presented in this deliverable.

⁶⁶ M. Crippa, E. Solazzo, D. Guizzardi, F. Monforti-Ferrario, F. N. Tubiello & A. Leip. 2021. *Food Systems Are Responsible for a Third of Global Anthropogenic GHG Emissions*; FAO, a c. di. 2016. *Forests and Agriculture. Land-Use Challenges and Opportunities*. State of the World's Forests 2016.

⁶⁷ J. Poore & T. Nemecek. 2018. *Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers*.

⁶⁸ FAO, a c. di. 2016. *Forests and Agriculture. Land-Use Challenges and Opportunities*. State of the World's Forests 2016.

⁶⁹ IPCC. 2019. *Summary for Policymakers. Special Report on Climate Change and Land*.

⁷⁰ Crippa, E. Solazzo, D. Guizzardi, F. Monforti-Ferrario, F. N. Tubiello & A. Leip. 2021. *Food Systems Are Responsible for a Third of Global Anthropogenic GHG Emissions*.

⁷¹ UNEP. 2021. *UNEP Food Waste Index Report 2021*; Vasileios Rizos, Julie Bryhn, Monica Alessi, Edoardo Righetti, Noriko Fujiwara & Cristian Stroia. 2021. *Barriers and Enablers for Implementing Circular Economy Business Models. Evidence from the Electrical and Electronic Equipment and Agri-Food Value Chains*.

⁷² A.-S. Bauer, M. Tacker, I. Uysal-Unalan, R.M.S. Cruz, T. Varzakas & V. Krauter. 2021. *Recyclability and Redesign Challenges in Multilayer Flexible Food Packaging*.

⁷³ OECD. 2019. *Business Models for the Circular Economy. Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*.

⁷⁴ Augusto Bianchini, Jessica Rossi & Marco Pellegrini. 2019. *Overcoming the Main Barriers of Circular Economy Implementation through a New Visualization Tool for Circular Business Models*.

In general terms, a business model describes how a firm generates, captures, and delivers value.⁷⁵ It provides a simplified representation of the elements constituting a complex organisational system, the interactions between them, and how they relate to the organisation's business logic.⁷⁶ In other words, a business model represents a firm's competitive strategy.⁷⁷

Circular business models aim to integrate principles of circular economy (reuse, reduce, recycle) into the business model design, to internalise the social and environmental costs of materials and products and optimise resource value.⁷⁸

In addition to minimising the use of natural resource inputs, circular business models differentiate from traditional ones also for different approaches across the value chain.⁷⁹ For instance, a circular sales strategy tends to focus on providing higher-quality products rather than maximising the sales volume of short-lived ones. Another common circular strategy consists of providing access to shared products, rather than the proper ownership. Furthermore, circular businesses tend to supply customers with additional repair and remanufacturing services, to maximise the value of existing materials and foster customer loyalty.

The growing literature on circular business models provides a great variety of approaches and definitions. Among existing taxonomies, we focus on the one adopted by the OECD⁸⁰, which categorized circular activities according to the underlying business proposition. In its report, the OECD identifies five major business models: *circular supply models*, *resource recovery models*, *product life extension models*, *sharing models*, and *product service system models*. Figure 5 summarises the key features of the mentioned circular business, while Figure 6 illustrates their impact on the linear economy value chain.

⁷⁵ Alexander Osterwalder, Yves Pigneur & Christopher L. Tucci. 2005. *Clarifying Business Models. Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept*.

⁷⁶ Martin Geissdoerfer, Sandra Naomi Morioka, Marly Monteiro de Carvalho & Steve Evans. 2018. *Business Models and Supply Chains for the Circular Economy*; Alexander Osterwalder, Yves Pigneur & Christopher L. Tucci. 2005. *Clarifying Business Models. Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept*.

⁷⁷ OECD. 2019. *Business Models for the Circular Economy. Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*.

⁷⁸ Anne P. M. Velenturf & Phil Purnell. 2021. *Principles for a Sustainable Circular Economy*.

⁷⁹ OECD. 2019. *Business Models for the Circular Economy. Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*.

⁸⁰ Ibid.

	Circular supply	Resource recovery	Product life extension	Sharing	Product service system
Key characteristic	Replace traditional material inputs with renewable, bio-based, recovered ones	Produce secondary raw materials from waste	Extend product lives	Increase utilisation of existing products and assets	Provision of services rather than products. Product ownership remains with supplier
Resource efficiency driver	Close material loops	Close material loops	Slow material loops	Narrow resource flows	Narrow resource flows
Business model sub-types	Cradle to cradle	Industrial symbiosis	Classic long life	Co-ownership	Product-oriented
		Recycling	Direct reuse	Co-access	User-oriented
		Upcycling	Repair		Result-oriented
		Downcycling	Refurbishment		
Main sectors currently applied in	Diverse consumer product sectors	Metals	Automotive	Short term lodging	Transport
		Paper and pulp	Heavy machinery	Transport	Chemicals
		Plastics	Electronics	Machinery	Energy
				Consumer products	

Figure 5: The Impact of Circular Business Models on a Linear Economy (OECD, 2019)

In the context of Agro2Circular, we recognize the *circular supply models* and the *resource recovery models* as the most relevant business modes for our project.

Circular supply business models differentiate from linear models by replacing traditional inputs with more sustainable alternatives, such as bio-based, renewable, or recovered materials. In this way, adopting firms can simultaneously reduce the environmental pressures of their supply chains while ensuring that input materials do not eventually become waste. In this sense, this approach also reflects the logic of the resource recovery model where material recovery is considered at an earlier stage. The advantages of adopting such business models include the possibility to reduce risks from the introduction of more stringent environmental regulation or risks from using natural resources which are geographically concentrated in a small number of countries. In addition, by replacing traditional inputs with more sustainable alternatives, firms can label their products as “green” and broaden their market to environmentally conscious consumers.

To design a circular supply agri-food business, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation suggests firms to opt for inputs and ingredients that: are more diverse (expanding the range of ingredients increases the genetic diversity of crops and livestock and improves resilience); are upcycled (to maximise return on invested inputs, as land and energy); have a lower environmental impact (for instance, by shifting from animal proteins to plant proteins); are regeneratively produced (regenerative agriculture comprise a set of context-dependent practices which increase total food output while generating climate and biodiversity benefits).⁸¹

The core strategy of *resource recovery business models* is to produce secondary raw materials from waste streams. The model includes three different activities: collection, sorting, and secondary production. These activities are generally carried out by different actors. In most cases, the collection of waste material is organised by local governments and the secondary production by private firms, while the sort of waste streams could be carried out by either public facilities or the private sector. The resource recovery processes can assume different variations, such as downcycling, which implies producing inferior quality raw material, upcycling, which creates superior quality raw material, and closed loop recycling (or industrial symbiosis), where the secondary raw material becomes an input for another manufacturing process.

Considering food production, recently there has been an increasing interest in the development of processing technologies for food waste reuse and recycling.⁸² Among the most effective applications, food waste can be used as fertilisers, which would reduce the need for synthetic and more expensive alternatives.⁸³ Additional applications include using food waste as compost to nourish the soil, as bioplastic or textile fibres⁸⁴, as biogas, and as animal feed.⁸⁵

To support the development and implementation of circular business models, several visualisation tools have been defined, based on the traditional version of the business model canvas. A business model canvas is a common practice to visualise how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value and it is commonly a crucial step in the process of business development.⁸⁶ According to Osterwalder, Pigneur, and Tucci (2005), a business model consists of nine elements, respectively: value proposition; target customer;

⁸¹ Ellen Macarthur Foundation. 2021. *The Big Food Redesign*.

<https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/news/the-big-food-redesign-new-study-launched-today>

⁸² Vasileios Rizos, Julie Bryhn, Monica Alessi, Edoardo Righetti, Noriko Fujiwara & Cristian Stroia. 2021. *Barriers and Enablers for Implementing Circular Economy Business Models. Evidence from the Electrical and Electronic Equipment and Agri-Food Value Chains*.

⁸³ UNEP. 2021. *UNEP Food Waste Index Report 2021*.

⁸⁴ Jesus Esteban & Miguel Ladero. 2018. *Food Waste as a Source of Value-Added Chemicals and Materials. A Biorefinery Perspective*.

⁸⁵ Kumarasamy Murugesan, Kaarmukhnilavan R. Srinivasan, Kowsalya Paramasivam, Ammayappan Selvam & Jonathan Wong. 2021. *Chapter Eleven - Conversion of Food Waste to Animal Feeds*. In: *Current Developments in Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, Published by Jonathan Wong, Guneet Kaur, Mohammad Taherzadeh, Ashok Pandey & Katia Lasaridi.

⁸⁶ Alexander Osterwalder, Yves Pigneur & Christopher L. Tucci. 2005. *Clarifying Business Models. Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept*; Anja-Tatjana Braun, Oliver Schöllhammer & Bernd Rosenkranz. 2021. *Adaptation of the business model canvas template to develop business models for the circular economy*; Alexander Osterwalder & Yves Pigneur. 2010. *Business Model Generation. A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers*.

distribution channel; relationship with different customer segments; value configuration; core competency; partner network; cost structure; revenue model. The following table summarises these elements.

Elements of Business Model	Description
Value proposition	Gives an overall view of a company's bundle of products and services.
Target customer	Describes the segments of customers a company wants to offer value to.
Distribution channel	Describes the various means of the company to get in touch with its customers.
Relationship	Explains the kind of links a company establishes between itself and its different customer segments.
Value configurations	Describes the arrangement of activities and resources.
Core competency	Outlines the competencies necessary to execute the company's business model.
Partner network	Portrays the network of cooperative agreements with other companies necessary to efficiently offer and commercialise value.
Cost structure	Sums up the monetary consequences of the means employed in the business model.
Revenue model	Describes the way a company makes money through a variety of revenue flows.

In the context of circular economy, a set of adaptations of the traditional business model canvas proposed by Osterwalder et al. (2005) have been developed to include social, environmental, and economic aspects.⁸⁷ In fact, circular solutions can produce a set of non-monetary benefits which are not easy to quantify and are often overlooked.⁸⁸ Adding these components to the canvas is a way to incorporate also these social and environmental elements and take them into account during the development of the business model.

For instance, the canvas developed in the context of the "Route to Circular Economy" project (funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 research) expands the traditional nine elements of business models to include two additional ones, regarding the social and environmental impacts (costs and benefits) of business activity.⁸⁹ The objective of this canvas is to highlight the importance of sustainability and circularity in providing value to people and the planet.

Another example is the Ecocanvas developed by Daou et al. (2020). In contrast to the previous example, the Ecocanvas does not focus on the impact of business activities, but it expands the economic-centred approach of the original canvas by including external business challenges, which concern legal, environmental, and social forces. Current and expected economic and legal challenges may refer to the introduction of more stringent

⁸⁷ Anja-Tatjana Braun, Oliver Schöllhammer & Bernd Rosenkranz. 2021. *Adaptation of the business model canvas template to develop business models for the circular economy*.

⁸⁸ CCRI. 2022. *Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale*.

⁸⁹ Shona McDermott, Doug Morwood, Pavel Laczko, Raymond Slaughter & Aleya Smith-Gillespie. s.d. *Circular Business Model Innovation Toolkit*.

environmental regulations (e.g. emission tax), market innovations, and macroeconomic fluctuations. The second group describes environmental challenges that have the potential to directly affect a business' production activities or the related supply chain, such as water scarcity, climate change, and increasing levels of pollution. Finally, societal and technological challenges refer to cultural and technological shifts affecting customers' behaviour over time. This extension of the traditional canvas would facilitate businesses in both identifying external key drivers of change and, subsequently, in taking the appropriate measures to embrace eco-innovation and improve the organisation's long-term competitiveness.

Recently, the key drivers guiding the adoption of circular business models have been: the intensification of business risks from operating a linear production model (e.g. stability of the supply chain and new regulation), technological developments, that are reducing the cost structure of circular activities, and the shift of consumers preferences towards more sustainable alternatives.⁹⁰ Despite these forces, in most sectors, the market penetration of the circular business model is still moderate (around 5-10%).⁹¹

On the other side, several barriers, both internal and external, influence the adoption and the scale-up of circular businesses. Considering the classification proposed by Bianchini et al. (2019), challenges faced while implementing a circular business model regard a wide range of aspects, such as internal processes (e.g. efforts in redefining business strategy); technical barriers (e.g. the need for technical and know-how expertise); market barriers (e.g. lack of supply network support); institutional, regulatory and social barriers (e.g. misaligned incentives); financial and economic barriers (e.g. need for long time investment and costly management processes).

In addition, the authors point out that the success of a circular business directly depends on a network of companies acting together to close material loops. Since the involved stakeholders are interdependent but independent, a network of information and feedback information is crucial to reduce the innate uncertainties of circular business strategies (ibid).

Focusing on the agri-food sector, the Centre for European Policy Studies has conducted an in-depth analysis by interviewing 41 case-study companies involved in the EU-funded CIRC4Life project to identify the main challenges faced when implementing circular activities. According to the collected results, policy and regulation along with financial and economic factors have been identified as decisive obstacles by the majority of companies.

Policy-related barriers refer to difficulties arising from bureaucracy and administration. For instance, getting official recognition for a circular process that uses leftovers from food production may entail excessive administrative requirements and disincentivise companies to use these inputs. Finance and economic factors mainly concern two aspects. Firstly, implementing more sustainable and circular approaches may entail a higher cost, for instance from the collection and treatment of side streams from food production. Secondly, the lack of access to financial resources is experienced as a major obstacle for agri-food

⁹⁰ OECD. 2019. *Business Models for the Circular Economy. Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*; Inga Uvarova, Dzintra Atstāja & Viola Korpa. 2020. *Challenges of the introduction of circular business models withing rural SMEs of EU*.

⁹¹ OECD. 2019. *Business Models for the Circular Economy. Opportunities and Challenges for Policy*.

businesses, especially in the early stage of business development, where additional support is crucial to make new processes financially sustainable.

In fact, the financial support needed from the circular business varies depending on its development and implementation stage: R&D (pre-revenue), start-up (pre-profit), scale-up (pre-profit to profit), growth (profit) and mature (stable income). Analysing the business and financial model of a circular solution is a useful approach to determine its funding and financing needs along these stages.⁹²

A business and financial analysis implies to identify the relevant costs and expenses deriving from the implementation of the solution, the cash-flows and revenues expected from its adoption, and assess its overall financial sustainability. It also requires to map and identify the available funding opportunities and the financial schemes that can support its development and implementation, considering public and private sources.

The funding programmes and financing schemes presented in D7.14 represent relevant examples that could be leveraged to support the development and adoption of circular solutions. In the following phases of the Agro2Circular project, a deeper investigation into the business models and the possible financing schemes to be adopted for the solutions developed in the project will be performed and will inform the results of the next deliverable on financing recommendations.

⁹² CCRI. 2022. *Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale.*

9. Good Practices

This chapter presents good practices of financing schemes for the circular economy. The good practices were selected in an effort to show the diversity of financing sources, methods and regional distribution in Europe. However, it should not be hidden that a key criterion for their selection was the availability of information.

In addition, the follow-up deliverable to this draft – D7.15 Financing Recommendations – will give greater prominence to regional good practices, particularly from Murcia.

9.1 CIRCWASTE (Finland)

Demonstrating the collaboration between 20 partners, the “LIFE IP on waste - towards circular economy in Finland” (CIRCWASTE)⁹³ project running between 01 October 2016 and 31 December 2023, aims to position Finland as a forerunner in circular economy by implementing the country’s National Waste Management Plan. The project is recognised as a good practice by the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform “because of its intervention methodology, its collaborative capacity, and its results.”⁹⁴

Of particular interest is the involvement of 5 research institutes and universities, 12 municipalities and regions, as well as 8 private companies and public enterprises in carrying out 20 project actions across 6 themes which include:

- Regional strategic development and networking projects,
- Resource efficiency in construction,
- Biodegradable waste and by-flows,
- Industrial waste and material flows,
- Utilising soils, and
- Digital solutions and logistics.

All together, these partners have a total budget of €18,521,507 with an EU contribution of €11,112,904 from the EU LIFE Programme. Nine other Finnish institutions are co-financing the project. This collaborative approach not only in terms of project participants but also in funding, shows that greater success is achieved when multiple stakeholders are involved as the project has helped reach national and EU targets with regard to transitioning to a circular economy.

9.2 URBIOFIN (Greece)

Composed of 15 partners from Spain, Denmark, Belgium, France, Greece and the Netherlands, the URBIOFIN project (Demonstration of an integrated innovative biorefinery for the transformation of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) into new BioBased products) aims to transform urban solid waste into new bioproducts demonstrated through a biorefinery

⁹³ https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/index.cfm?fuseaction=search.dspPage&n_proj_id=6098

⁹⁴ <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/financing-circular-economy>

concept.⁹⁵ The project utilized three modules which resulted in the daily conversion of about 10 tonnes of the organic fraction of MSW into chemical building blocks, biopolymers, and additives. Throughout the process, the project utilized green technologies that resulted in an efficient, circular and zero-waste valorisation of what would have been typical organic waste products of a municipality. These project results can make a valuable contribution to raising awareness among potential consumers of the benefits of using biobased products. On one hand, the integrated biorefinery reflects the environmentally friendly image of the new biobased processes, while on the other hand contributes to reducing the organic fraction of waste going to landfills and achieving the objectives of the Waste Framework Directive.

The URBIOFIN project received funding under the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU) within the EU Horizon 2020 programme with a total budget of €15 million. The solutions were implemented from 01 June 2017 to 30 September 2022.

9.3 EIB Financed Projects

9.3.1 Novamont Renewable Chemistry, Italy

The project involves the financing of investments for the development of an integrated supply chain in the field of biochemicals and bioplastics. The EIB's proposed financing amounts to some €30 million. The project concerns the use of innovative process technologies to produce bioplastics and biochemicals to be used for a range of applications in industry (e.g., plasticisers, biodegradable lubricating oils for industry and vehicles) and consumer goods (e.g., renewable and biodegradable bases for cosmetics, carrier bags, films and packaging).⁹⁶

9.3.2 ISP Loan for Circular Economy, Italy

The scheme allows circular economy projects to be implemented by SMEs and mid-cap companies through a framework loan. To receive co-financing, projects must demonstrate the use of different circular business models that aim to, as an example, preserve the value of products and materials for as long as possible and minimise resource consumption and waste generation.⁹⁷ These projects are to be implemented in different sectors such as food, energy, mobility, fashion, built environment, consumer goods and industrial manufacturing.

9.3.3 IREN Climate Action and Circular Economy Loan, Italy

The programme focuses on the financing of projects on the solid waste and hydropower sectors.⁹⁸ These projects are thus considered as investments on efforts to counteract climate change and promote circularity.

⁹⁵ <https://www.urbiofin.eu/>

⁹⁶ <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20150447>

⁹⁷ <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20180715>

⁹⁸ <https://www.eib.org/en/projects/pipelines/all/20190156>

Specifically, investments on projects related to solid waste management will be implemented in the regions of Liguria, Piedmont and Reggio Emilia. Examples of financed actions include, among others, a plant to produce pallets from wood waste and the purchase of new vehicles for waste collection. On the other hand, investments in the hydropower sector were implemented in 16 sites in the Piedmont and Campania regions.

9.3.4 Winnow, Romania

The food waste management company, Winnow, will develop and introduce EIB funds worth EUR7.5m for the development of software and hardware solutions to help staff in commercial kitchens to reduce the amount and type of food wasted. The aim is to provide users with data for the management and prevention of food waste.

As part of the European Growth Finance Facility (EGFF), the loan scheme is designed to offer SMEs and mid-cap companies' investment in tangible and intangible assets thus achieving a positive crowding-in effect, attracting additional private investors to the companies.⁹⁹

9.3.5 Tackling Food Waste, France

Straying away from traditional food waste practices of paying other companies to either burn or dispose of unsold products in landfills, the French company, Phenix, has developed an innovative and digital alternative. The service allows companies to sell their food items just before its expiry date as well as help provide food donations to charities.¹⁰⁰ This scheme ensures that no food is wasted while money is saved not only on the food item itself but also with its waste disposal. This idea has also given businesses financial incentives such as tax credits when they donate to charities. Phenix has expanded their services to Portugal and Spain. Their idea has also received investments from Bpifrance in order to internationalize and grow further.

9.4 De Clique (Netherlands)

De Clique is a Dutch company that collects food by-products such as coffee grounds and other food waste from companies to resell them to third party suppliers and product manufacturers who transform them into new products such as food ingredients, cosmetics and biomaterials. In order to be more environmentally friendly, the collection process is carried out by bicycle couriers and electric vehicles. On the alternative, inedible food by-products and other organic waste are often landfilled or incinerated. The company thus guarantees the reuse of materials by collecting and separating waste into high-value products that last in the community economy.

⁹⁹ <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2019-251-investment-plan-for-europe-support-to-improve-food-management-in-romania>

¹⁰⁰ European Investment Bank. 2019. *Joint Initiative on Circular Economy* [Factsheet]. https://www.eib.org/attachments/joint_initiative_on_circular_economy_en.pdf

Currently, it estimates that only 2% of organic waste produced in cities is reused to make valuable products, which is a large untapped potential opportunity. This system helps to increase this figure to 10 tons per month by reducing dependence on finite resources.

9.5 GPP Good Practices

9.5.1 GPP in Flemish Governments Cooperation Agreement with Municipalities

During the years 2008-2013, the Flemish Department of Environment, Nature and Energy awarded grants to the municipalities that signed a cooperation agreement. Additional grants could be obtained on a voluntary basis through actions at the award or project level¹⁰¹. One of the ten topics covered was optimal ecological use, including the sustainable use of wood, certified waste in tenders and passive awareness. On the procurement level, environmentally friendly products should be used and promoted to the target groups (product groups are as follows: Compost, construction waste, materials from recycled plastics, office supplies, catering, environmentally friendly products, cleaning products, wood preservatives, paints and varnishes, products from recognized recycling points). GPP guidelines have been developed for these product groups. The projects approved were eligible for 50% funding. The evaluation was based on annual reports. For many municipalities, this marked the beginning of green procurement in their organization.

€30,000,000 in subsidies were needed. The number of grants depended on the inhabitants and the area of the municipality. The basis was €1.7/hour + €1.4/ha (minimum €20,000). The subsidy was €30,000 x the maximum number of full-time sustainability workers specified in the contract. Projects received €1.7/hour + €1.4/ha x 61.1%.¹⁰²

9.5.2 GPP Regional Plan, Liguria

The new Green Public Procurement Plan is based on the previous strategy and was developed to raise awareness of the circular economy and its application in the regional market by increasing the participation of SMEs in tenders and improving their knowledge of green certifications.¹⁰³ The main objective is to implement green procurement by including CAM (minimum environmental criteria) in public tenders for goods and services. The plan is innovative and includes training for public administration and the private sector. On the public administration side, this project aims to promote capacity building for the preparation and evaluation of green tenders. The private sector, for its part, will promote capacity building in companies for environmental sustainability criteria and certification. Under this framework, SMEs will have to acquire knowledge and adopt European sustainability tools such as EMAS, PEF, EU ECOLABEL and LCA studies. In fact, the existence of these EU instruments, in particular EMAS, is rewarded in the evaluation of tenders. The plan promotes

¹⁰¹ <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/gpp-in-flemish-governments-cooperation-agreement-with-municipalities>

¹⁰² <https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/nl>

¹⁰³ <https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/enhance/news/news-article/14499/enhance-and-the-new-gpp-plan-of-the-liguria-region/>

the use of European sustainability instruments to foster the recovery and increase the resilience of SMEs and the regional and national market after the Covid-19 pandemic.

The project and its entire implementation required about 35,000 euros and the participation of 4 members. The rest of the additional activities such as stakeholder meetings, training, etc. required about 15,000 euros and the hiring of 2 staff.¹⁰⁴

9.5.3 Promotion of Green Public Procurement by Providing Green Technical Specifications, Lithuania

The Central Procurement Organisation (CPO LT) is the body in charge of procurement, both at the national and local level, on behalf of the contracting authorities.¹⁰⁵ Acquisitions are conducted through the CPO LT electronic catalogue, which minimizes the procurement procedure, optimizes the purchasing cycles, and reduce the costs of the process. This is structured into 49 different groups within the categories of services, goods and works.

Through this methodology, it is possible to determine which technical specifications are necessary to qualify for green public procurement. This facilitates the process of green public procurement, as it is not necessary for the contracting organizations to establish the criteria themselves. In addition, these entities have the possibility to use these technical specifications as an example and carry out this process themselves.

99% of procurements are carried out using green specifications. There are 380 ecological specifications for categories such as office supplies, cleaning services, IT and office equipment, cell phones, furniture, and foodstuffs.

During the first half of 2020, ecological goods and services acquired through the CPO LT e-catalogue achieved a total value of €18 million.¹⁰⁶

9.5.4 Good Practices in Green Public Procurement in Regional Waste Management, Spain

CREA oversees waste management in the districts of Vinalopó, Spain. One of the main environmental problems is the huge amount of waste that is landfilled and cannot be recycled.¹⁰⁷ As a solution, CREA aims to reduce the amount of waste by recycling and classifying the waste generated for subsequent recovery or reintroduction into the value chain. This project is particularly essential in densely populated areas, where there are environmental problems related to poor waste management and uncontrolled landfills. All municipalities are required to have an environmental plan that includes green procurement measures tailored to the needs and reality of the municipality.

¹⁰⁴ https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1655473732.pdf

¹⁰⁵ <https://www2.cpo.lt/en/eu-support/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/promotion-of-green-public-procurement-by-providing-green-technical-specifications>

¹⁰⁷ <https://elretodelreciclaje.com/crea-consorci-de-residus/>

10. Recommendations

- To redirect financial resources from linear to circular solutions, negative externalities need to be systematically priced in as circular businesses would benefit from corresponding price signals.
- The private sector should not be forced to share or promote sustainability, rather reinforcing the idea that it should be based above all on business opportunities rather than just legal obligation or conviction. Not harming the environment or the climate is not just a matter of corporate social responsibility, the circular economy is a business opportunity for the private sector.
- The creation of reporting standards for circular businesses and the adoption of some standardised reporting measures would reduce asymmetric information and distortions that hinder the growth of circular investments.
- The lack of credible commitments from the public sector poses a risk to long-term investment decisions by private sector actors that needs to be addressed.
- The search for financing opportunities for the circular economy should not be limited to government support or incentives, but should also consider different business models, loans, and private sector support. Although public funding is widely available in this area, it is not possible to finance all projects. Business models with a high sustainability contribution can receive funding from the private sector through a win-win relationship.
- It is also possible to find investments in innovative ideas with alternative mechanisms such as crowdfunding. Small investors can use such mechanisms to make all their investments. Moreover, a business idea can be promoted at the same time thanks to the large audience it reaches.
- If there are no grant opportunities for investments in the circular economy or if there is no suitable programme at regular intervals, the loans granted by investment banks or private banks should be considered. Since such loans are supported by certain consortia or the public sector, they offer the chance to find financing that is more suitable than the market conditions.
- When looking for funding for projects, it helps companies to find the right fund if they first define the focus of their activities. This is because each programme has its own priorities and funding mechanisms. For example, if the project idea is more of a research and modelling project or a pilot application, it would make sense to use the tendering opportunities of the Horizon Europe programme.
- The legal status of a project organisation can affect the use of the programmes. Some programmes are only suitable for public institutions or non-governmental organisations, while others are suitable for for-profit organisations. When applying for the programmes, these criteria need to be checked.
- The circular economy concept is inherently a multi-stakeholder approach that involves many processes. Therefore, giving high priority to stakeholder participation and collective collaboration in the formulation of projects will help them gain clout and attract more funding.
- Cooperation between actors in the field of the environment or circular economy is called to be a line of work for the present and for the future. Companies can use the

sub-products of other firms, this will enable cooperation between companies that had always presented cultural barriers, at least in Spain (win-win approach).

- When developing business models for the circular economy, the positive and negative effects of incentives in the market and financial analysis need to be considered. This is because the additional support received for transactions during the operational process may shorten the return on investments. On the contrary, business models may become less profitable due to additional obstacles they encounter.
- The recycling and upcycling rate of organic products is still very low, which means that there is still a long way to go in this area, which holds investment potential. If considering the principles of waste prevention, sharing systems and the win-win principle when developing business models, they will have a high chance of success and minimise harm to nature.
- The importance of technological partners (i.e., technological centres and other research and technology organisations) promoting technology and knowledge transfer, and the implementation of new methods, advanced materials, and improved processes in enterprises, in order to accelerate industrial transition towards a green economy.
- Investments should contribute to the extension of product life cycles and the reuse of waste and the valorisation of sub-products in line with EU regulations to support the transition to a circular economy.
- Investments should contribute to reducing and optimising water resources so that adequate ecological levels are maintained in aquifers and basins.
- Investments should contribute to reducing all forms of pollution that negatively impact ecosystems and human health.
- Investments should contribute to protecting or restoring biodiversity and achieving good ecosystem status.

10.1 Green Public Procurement

- GPP is also a kind of incentive and an important tool for actors to achieve a positive external impact on nature. Public institutions can use their purchasing power to put pressure on suppliers to achieve positive environmental impacts through GPP.
- Supplier should comply with GPP criteria as soon as possible to stay ahead of the competition, because the number of institutions requiring these criteria is increasing by the day. Many environmentally friendly applications that are preferred today will be mandatory tomorrow.
- Environmental aspects and opportunities to apply green procurement criteria should be considered in all procurement processes, especially in terms of reducing energy consumption (electricity, heat and water) and emissions (CO₂ emissions and particulates), recyclability, life extension, material selection, use of recycled materials and waste prevention.
- Possibilities for buying used products and products made from recycled materials should be considered.

- The products procured should be recyclable and sent for reuse or recycling after use.
- Life-cycle costs should be taken into account in procurement. This allows procurers to choose the most economically advantageous option on a life-cycle basis.
- Resource-efficient procurement options should be considered. These include the procurement of services instead of products, optional forms of ownership and the reuse of products.
- Eco-label criteria can be used when formulating tenders.

11. Annex

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